

WHAT ARE THE 5 THINGS YOU SHOULD KNOW ABOUT SPIDER VEINS?

A red or blue spiderweb-like network of tiny veins, this condition is also known as Telangiectasias which appears on the legs or on the face of people. Though they appear mostly on the face or legs, they can actually be found on any part of the body. This condition is sadly a very common one. All around the world millions of people suffering from this condition. In North America, [vein specialist california](#) reported that about 40% of women have one form of vein condition or another. It also states that by the age of 80, 80% of women will have one form of vein condition or another.

How Can Spider Veins Be Identified?

Other than the obvious network of red or blue veins that appear on the skin, only a **vein specialist** or a dermatologist can perform a thorough check and properly advise the patient.

How Can Veins Disease Be Treated?

Technology has afforded us very effective yet simple **vein treatments** for this and other vein diseases. We shall focus on the most effective methods which are in use today. Only mildly invasive methods will be accommodated by the patient's health insurance. These procedures are painless and require no extensive recovery period as a patient can be back at work the same day after treatment. The **spider vein treatment** will consist of one or both laser treatments or treatment with a salt solution called a sclerosant.

Laser Therapy

For the **spider vein treatment california**, it is the most effective and easy method. It is painless therefore requires no form of anesthesia and is minimally invasive. It requires little to no recovery time. This procedure is easily performed at the vein treatment memorial in the out-patients unit and is very gentle. Hence, it is suitable for any sensitive parts of the body.

Sclerotherapy

This method is also a very effective, mildly invasive procedure. It can also be performed in the out-patients unit without anesthesia. The injection of sclerosant is given into the veins. The sclerosant causes the veins to harden clear. This process is quick and effective.

What Causes Spider Veins?

The main cause of spider veins is due to, the valves of veins are not working properly. The walls of the veins weaken or the vein valves begin to weaken for any reason, in response to the gravitational pull the blood could begin to flow away from the heart. This will result in blood pooling in the legs.

How Can Spider Veins Be Prevented?

There are certain things that [spider vein treatment near me california](#), suggests to reduce the risk of spider veins appearing on our bodies. You can do perform certain things on daily basis to slow down the process. The things which you should do to prevent spider veins include:

- Regular exercise
- Healthy diet
- Adequate hydration

- Maintain an appropriate blood pressure
- Wear compression socks
- Avoid prolonged exposure to the sun.

If they are already on display, it is very important for you to seek **vein treatment near me** help. The treatment for this condition is readily available and can be covered by most health insurance policies. Nip the problem in the bud and avoid enjoy a confident and comfortable life. help. The treatment for this condition is readily available and can be covered by most health insurance policies. Nip the problem in the bud and avoid enjoy a confident and comfortable life.